

Survival of the Trophont Stages of *Cryptocaryon irritans*, a Fish Protozoan Pathogen in Different Culture Medium

by

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Abstract

All stages in the life cycle of *Cryptocaryon irritans* were successfully cultured in different medium, without loss of viability. Survival and development of the stage were investigated in selected monophasic media at room temperature, 27°C. Among the three media tested, Hanks' media enhanced the highest rate of encystment and division of trophonts resulting in free moving tomites stages. In contrast Earle's and MEME media only able to support up to encystment stage and no further development stage was determined after that. Cysts maintained in Hanks' medium gave the maximum number of tomites (200-400) through asexual reproduction over an encystment duration of 7 days. The significance of the results is discussed with regard to the routine maintenance of the parasite and hence, the prospects of large scale production in vitro culture for future use.

Keywords: *Cryptocaryon irritans*, protozoan, *in vitro*, trophont, tomont, tomita, theront

Introduction

The economic impact of white spot disease, cryptocaryoniasis caused by the protozoan pathogen *Cryptocaryon irritans* on farmed sea bass has been tremendous and caused much concern in most countries. Hence, there is a need for work on the

prevention of this protozoan infection by biologics rather than the recommended administration of chemicals bath (especially formaldehyde) in cultured fish. Most chemotherapy failed since the tomont in an encysting stage is resistant to drugs while the trophonts are often buried deep in the fish tissue. Biological application like vaccination is an effective way to prevent fish diseases. As a preliminary step, there is a need to develop a suitable culture medium that could be used in large-scale production of the parasite for antigen production purposes. In view of that, experimental on the *in vitro* culture of this parasite was carried out.

Materials & Methods

The trophonts of *C. irritans* were collected from the infected hatchery reared sea bass. The infected fish were killed and the gills removed and placed in filtered seawater for the parasites to settle down. Trophonts were collected and rapidly transferred by pipette through three washes in sterile filtered seawater to remove associated host debris and to dilute the bacterial flora. Motile trophonts were selected and subject to three further washes in 10 cm³ of sterile filtered seawater. They were transferred to filtered seawater and some of modify balanced salt solution such as 1x Hanks' (HBSS), Minimum Essential Medium Eagle with Earle's salt without l-Glutamine (MEME) and 1x Earle's without Mg and Ca (EBSS) in 96-well plate, one per-well, and were incubated at room temperature. The development stages of trophonts were monitored and observed under inverted microscope and image analysis system.

Results & Discussion

The trophonts in 96-well plate encysted in all the three media as well as the sterile filtered seawater within 24 hours (Plate 1). The results of the survival of *C. irritans* from different media are showed in Table 1. No dead trophonts were found on day one in seawater, HBSS and MEME except in EBSS. On day 2, there were signs of cell division inside the thick-walled cyst and from day 5-7, moving tomites were

Plate 1: Encysted stages with the thick walled (arrow) in different culture medium on day one: (a) HBSS (b) EBSS (c) MEME and (d) Sterile seawater x20

observed in sterile seawater and HBSS (Plate 2). In the EBSS medium cell division was observed from day 3 up to day 6, but no tomites was produced. In contrast, no cell division of the trophont, which remain encysted up to day 9 in MEME media through out the

Plate 2: Development stages of the trophont of *C. irritans* in HBSS media. (a) Encystment stage on day 1 (b) Division stage on day 2 (c) Tomont stage containing numerous of tomites on day 5 (d) Active theronts within the cyst (e) Active theronts outside the cyst or upon release from the thick wall on day 5.

Table 1: Percentage of survival of *C. irritans* from different culture medium (in infectivity stage)

Day	Sterile Seawater				HBSS				EBSS				MEME			
	En	Div	To	De	En	Div	To	De	En	Div	To	De	En	Div	To	De
1	100	-	-	-	100	-	-	-	98.7	-	-	1.3	100	-	-	-
2	43.6	9.1	-	47.3	18.9	70.3	-	10.8	98.7	-	-	1.3	90.9	-	-	9.1
3	36.3	12.7	-	51.0	5.4	78.4	-	16.2	39.0	29.9	-	31.1	90.9	-	-	9.1
4	25.5	10.9	-	63.6	5.4	46.0	-	48.6	7.8	61.1	-	31.1	83.6	-	-	16.4
5	10.9	16.4	10.9	61.8	5.4	12.2	27.0	55.4	7.8	55.8	-	36.4	38.2	-	-	61.8
6	16.4	-	-	83.6	2.7	9.4	18.9	69.0	2.5	51.9	-	45.6	34.5	-	-	65.5
7	-	-	-	100	1.4	-	17.6	81.0	-	-	-	100	7.3	-	-	92.7
8	-	-	-	-	-	-	IT	100	-	-	-	-	7.3	-	-	92.7
9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.5	-	-	94.5
10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	100

*En – Encysted stage Div – Division stage To – Theronts stage De – Dead IT – Infectivity Trial

experimental period.

The life cycle of *C. irritans* involves four developmental stages namely as trophont (grows within the epidermis of the skin and gills of fish), tomont encystment (a trophont stage that leaves the host and secretes a cyst or a thick wall surround the body surface), division tomont (an encystment trophont undergoing cell divisions to form tomites), and theronts (individual cell in division tomont). Tomonts are characterised by a wall composed of several layers, and also by their unequal cell divisions. According to Colorni and Diamant (1993), they divide and develop into theronts in an asynchronous rate. The number of tomonts completing encystment, theronts produced per cyst and theronts subsequently surviving were found to be different in all the media tested. When the trophont was placed in the HBSS, EBSS and MEME media, it encysted on the first day. However, the encysted trophont in MEME medium did not show any sign of cell division, whereas it showed cell division in seawater, HBSS and EBSS media (Figure 1).

Reproduction in *C. irritans* is generally associated with the production of tomites during encystment, which differentiate into theronts. However, the detection of precystic trophont division here in culture may be indicative of a normal, although rarely observed event in the life cycle of this parasite. In the present study, it is suggested that reproduction may occur within the fish epidermis as recorded a single precystic division of trophonts following exit from the host epidermis and the subsequent normal encystment and development of the progeny. The mature trophont leaves the fish as a free-swimming tomont, secretes a cyst and undergoes multiple divisions to

produce tomites. Tomites emerge as infective free-swimming theronts that attach and penetrate into the skin and gill epithelia of susceptible fishes. The secretion of the cyst is usually completed within 24 hours in 25°C (Dickerson and Dawe, 1995).

Multiple divisions by budding were also recorded in culture, resulting in numerous small individuals, probably representing tomite production. Because of its thickness and hardness, the cyst wall of the tomont retains its original shape after swimming out of the tomites. According to Cheung *et al.*

(e.g., saltwater composition, growth temperature) or differences in parasite isolates and fishes between laboratories might account for these discrepancies. The present study showed that, the encystment stages took place within 24 hours in room temperature (27°C).

It is believed that the period for these stages could be shortened as compared with the finding by Xu *et al.* (1992). According to the author, the *C. irritans* trophonts only takes a few hours to develop into an individual cyst with several layers of wall and unequal cell divisions inside at room temperature. Hence, Diggles and Lester (1996) reported that tomonts took longer to excyst under low temperature. Yoshinaga and Dickerson (1994) also highlighted that in 24 to 27°C, *C. irritans* tomonts took 3 to 28 days to divide and produce infective theronts with most emerging by the eighth day. However, only Burgess and Matthews (1994) mentioned that during encystment the external environment is shown to be influenced by photoperiod, both these events occurring over the dark cycle.

The number of tomites found in this study was higher as compared with the range as reported by Dickerson and Dawe (1995). This could probably due to the higher temperature which promote the development and growth of trophont, enhance division and eventual release of a maximum number of infective tomites. *Cryptocaryon irritans* differs from its freshwater counterpart in that it generally takes longer time to reproduce and differentiate outside the fish. Secretion of the cyst is usually completed within 24 hours at 25°C. Cheung *et al.* (1979) found that only 10% of tomonts held in 7°C secreted cysts. When the

Fig. 1: Development pattern of *C. irritans* trophont in different medium. (The terminology used followed that by P.K.Woo)

(1979), successful reproduction in vitro requires the secretion of a cyst wall at least for the initial cycles of division. As observed in this study, we considered that any differences found, such as the extent and type of tomite growth and the size and structure of tomites produced, reflect the available nutrients and physical conditions. Variations in experimental conditions

organisms were incubated at 25°C, the majority (66%) secreted cysts. At 24 to 27°C, tomites take 3 to 28 days to divide and produce infective theronts with most emerging by the eighth day.

On the other hand, a study on *Ichthyophthirius multifiliis* by Ekless and Matthews (1993) showed that the concentrated media could delay encystment and the production of viable, sterile theronts, thus allowing a 4-day extension of the life cycle at 20°C. Further extensions of the life cycle of *I. multifiliis* may be achieved by lowering the temperature to below 20°C thereby increasing the duration of the life cycle (Nigrelli *et al.*, 1976). In the present study, HBSS media are able to support the growth and development of trophont into theront stages, thus ensuring the routine maintenance of the parasite and future prospects for in vitro culture.

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